

Numerical Simulation for Thermal Cycle Fatigue Failure for Composite Materials Based on Entropy Damage Criterion

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Background & Motivation

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) ¹⁾

- Excellent weight, strength and insulation properties
- Used in the aerospace and automotive industries
- Used in the housing of products that require insulation characteristics in line with the shift to EVs.

Issue

- CFRP components are often exposed to **thermal cycling**.
- Mismatch in thermal expansion coefficients between fibers and matrix resin generates **internal thermal stresses**.
- These stresses cause damage over time—especially transverse matrix cracks in cross-ply laminates.

Hashin's Failure Criterion

- **The Hashin's failure criterion is a damage model that allows the failure modes to be classified in four types in anisotropic materials such as CFRP.**

- **It classifies failure into four main modes:**

1) Fiber tensile 2) Fiber compression 3) Matrix tensile 4) Matrix compression

$$e_{ft} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13}}\right)^2$$

$$e_{fc} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_C}\right)^2$$

$$e_{mt} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_T}\right)^2 + \frac{\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{(S_{23})^2} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{S_{12}^2} + \frac{\tau_{13}^2}{S_{13}^2}$$

$$e_{mc} = \left[\left(\frac{Y_C}{2S_{23}}\right)^2 - 1\right] \frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_C} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{2S_{23}}\right)^2 + \frac{\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{S_{23}^2} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{S_{12}^2} + \frac{\tau_{13}^2}{S_{13}^2}$$

- **For each mode, independent criteria for damage initiation and evolution can be defined.**
- **This enables tracking of damage behavior in fibers, matrix, and shear separately, making it effective for reproducing complex failure under thermo-mechanical loading.**

Objective

- **Proposal of a Fracture Prediction Method for Thermal Loads Using the Hashin Failure Criterion**
 - To construct a simulation framework that evaluates failure initiation and progression in CFRP cross-ply laminates under thermal loading.
 - To apply the Hashin's failure criterion to separately capture fiber- and matrix-dominated damage modes.
 - To compare and discuss the experimental results and analytical results.

Calculation Summary

The three governing equations used in this study

- Calculate dissipated energy from dashpot deformation

$$\Delta W = \Delta b \sigma$$

- Entropy is defined as the value obtained from dividing dissipated energy by temperature.

$$S = S_{old} + \frac{\Delta W}{T}$$

- Time-temperature superposition principle. It expresses the behavior due to temperature increase by accelerating time.

$$\log \alpha^{TR} = \frac{\Delta H}{2.303R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_R} \right)$$

S	Entropy
W	Dissipated energy
Δb	Dashpot displacement increment
T	Temperature
T_R	Reference temperature
ΔH	Active energy
α^{TR}	Shift factor

Hashin's failure criteria

- Equations of Hashin's failure criteria shows relationship between stress and strength. (There are 4 damage modes.)
- Criterion satisfied ($e \geq 1$) → damage onset
- The damage variable increases from 0 to 1 after damage onset.
- Strength reduction is based on entropy damage.

Strength in Each Material Direction

X_{T,n_0}	X_{C,n_0}	Y_{T,n_0}	Y_{C,n_0}	S_{12,n_0}	S_{13,n_0}	S_{23,n_0}
3930	2775	150	200	117	117	117

(Unit of Strength is MPa.)

* X : Fiber Y : Matrix

Failure criteria

$$e_{ft} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_{T,n_0}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_{12,n_0}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{S_{13,n_0}} \right)^2$$

$$e_{fc} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_{C,n_0}} \right)^2$$

$$e_{mt} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_{T,n_0}} \right)^2 + \frac{\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{(S_{23,n_0})^2} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{(S_{12,n_0})^2} + \frac{\tau_{13}^2}{(S_{13,n_0})^2}$$

$$e_{mc} = \left[\left(\frac{Y_{C,n_0}}{2S_{23,n_0}} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_{C,n_0}} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{2S_{23,n_0}} \right)^2 + \frac{\tau_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{(S_{23,n_0})^2} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{(S_{12,n_0})^2} + \frac{\tau_{13}^2}{(S_{13,n_0})^2}$$

Strength reduction

$$X_{T,n_0} = (1 - \alpha_{AT}S_{n_0})X_{T,0}, \quad X_{C,n_0} = (1 - \alpha_{AC}S_{n_0})X_{C,0},$$

$$Y_{T,n_0} = (1 - \alpha_{OT}S_{n_0})Y_{T,0}, \quad Y_{C,n_0} = (1 - \alpha_{OC}S_{n_0})Y_{C,0},$$

$$S_{12,n_0} = (1 - \alpha_{OS}S_{n_0})S_{12,0}, \quad S_{13,n_0} = (1 - \alpha_{OS}S_{n_0})S_{13,0},$$

$$S_{23,n_0} = (1 - \alpha_{OS}S_{n_0})S_{23,0}$$

Fracture energy reduction

$$G_{ft,n_0} = (1 - \alpha_{AT}S_{n_0})^2 G_{ft,0}, \quad G_{fc,n_0} = (1 - \alpha_{AC}S_{n_0})^2 G_{fc,0},$$

$$G_{mt,n_0} = (1 - \alpha_{OT}S_{n_0})^2 G_{mt,0}, \quad G_{mc,n_0} = (1 - \alpha_{OC}S_{n_0})^2 G_{mc,0}$$

ft	fc	mt	mc
Fiber tension	Fiber compression	Matrix tension	Matrix compression

Damage Onset Criterion

Damage Evolution Calculation Flow

● No damage consideration

● At damage initiation

● Current state

◆ Damage Evolution Procedure

• ② = ① / (Degradation at damage initiation)

• ③ = 2 × G / ②

• ④ = ② × (Current degradation)

• ⑤ : ④ = ③ : ②

• $d = \frac{⑤(⑥ - ④)}{⑥(⑤ - ④)}$

✓ α can be divided into 7 modes:

Tensile/Compression in fiber direction, Tensile/Compression in matrix direction, and shear.

✓ The calculation uses only the initial fracture energy.

Numerical Model of CFRP Cross-Ply Laminate

➤ Overview of the Analysis

- CFRP laminate with $[0_2/90_4/0_2]$
- Lay-up Element size: $0.2 \text{ mm} \times 0.2 \text{ mm} \times 0.2 \text{ mm}$
- Randomized tensile strength in the resin using Weibull distribution

✓ The Weibull distribution

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \left\{ \ln \left(\frac{1}{1-R} \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{m}}$$

	Symbol	Value
Weibull parameter	m	7
Scaling parameter	σ_0	90 MPa

Numerical Model of CFRP Cross-Ply Laminate

➤ Overview of the Analysis

- Heat cycle the model temperature between 400K and 200K, Period 2s.
- The reference temperature is set to 400 K.

The Outer side

The Outer side

The Inner side

The Inner side

The Inner side

Analysis results

Damage condition of the 0° ply

Damage condition after 1 cycle

Damage condition after 3 cycles

A crack initially appeared at the edge, followed by its gradual propagation

Stress distribution according to damage condition (0° ply)

Stress distribution after thermal cyclic loadings.

Stress condition before damage starts

Stress condition after 3 cycles

It can be seen that the stress distribution changes due to the formation of cracks.

Damage condition of the 90° ply

Damage condition after 1 cycle

Damage condition after 3 cycles

Compared to the 0-degree ply, damage was more pronounced at the edge, followed by similar propagation

Stress distribution according to damage condition (90° ply)

Distribution of stress values in the tensile direction of the resin

Stress condition before damage starts

Stress condition after 3 cycles

Here too, the stress distribution changed as the damage progressed. It was particularly noticeable in the cracked areas.

Summary of analysis results

- **Matrix crack formation was successfully reproduced through numerical simulation.**
- **Stress distribution changes caused by crack formation were successfully observed.**
- **Entropy-based damage criterion is effective for predicting CFRP failure under thermal loading.**

Comparison with Experimental Results:

Left: Laminate surface after thermal cycling.

Right: Visualization of cracks in 0° and 90° plies, overlaid with transparency.

The model successfully captures the grid-like crack pattern observed experimentally, at least partially.

Conclusion

- **A numerical simulation framework was developed to model thermal fatigue failure in cross-ply CFRP laminates.**
- **The model incorporates an entropy-based damage criterion, enabling:**
 - **Prediction of transverse matrix cracking under thermal cycling**
 - **Damage progression under thermal load**
- **Simulation results show:**
 - **Progressive increase in entropy and damage with thermal cycles**
 - **Matrix cracking and stiffness degradation were observed during thermal cycling**